

Ethnocentrism correlates with Cyberbullying: Afghan Facebook users

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Abstract: Ethnocentric and cyberbullying behaviors are the trigger point of Afghan nationals. It is important to study ethnocentrism and Facebook's Cyberbullying behavior. Voluntarily participants of both gender took part and they were from different ethnicities such as Tajik, Pashtun, Hazara, Uzbek, and other minorities (54.8%, 28%, 4.5%, 9.9%, 2.8%) respectively. A purposive sampling technique was used for participants' selection. The sample comprised of N=425 participants which consist of Kunduz province and other provinces (375, 101) respectively and its age ranged from (18-36) years. Moreover, Ethnocentrism Scale and Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI) were used for data collection.

The correlational research design used for data analysis. On average males were using Facebook (125.4 minutes/day) and females (81.44 minutes/day). The result revealed that ethnocentrism has a significant positive correlation with cyberbullying and cyber victimization, while other factors, age, and gender did not show a significant difference. Lastly, the study revealed that correlation between the Cyberbullying & Cyber victimization had a strong significant uphill positive linear relationship.

Key words: Cyberbullying, Facebook, Ethnicity, Ethnocentrism

1. Introduction

Hegemony is a natural phenomenon but priority on one individual over other creates lots of problems. In some cases, individuals give hegemony to clans, tribes, nations, and sometimes this causes many problems such as bullying, abuse, fight, taunting, etc. The meaning of "Ethnocentrism" term is making judgments about another culture solely by the values and standards of one's own culture.

On other hand, technology brought many facilities. It has both positive and negative impacts. Exactly it is up to the users how they use it. When somebody misuses technology, it is presumed because of ethnicity and cultural values. Recently the social networking sites have brought a new era of communication to this world. There are many social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp, which allow people to interact and connect with other people across the globe. Cyberbullying is the new phenomenon of the new era. Enhancing technologies brought a new era of problems and challenges to society. This could affect different strata of Afghan society such as gender, age, and other factors. For example in a case, Tahmina Arian launched a moment "#whereismyname". At the time she has been cyber victimized. Overall, misbehavior has happened for "religious, political, and ethnic" factors [1, p. 44].

Cyberbullying is one of the growing challenges for Afghan society in social network sites. Cyberbullying is the usage of electronic communication to bully a person. Just by sending messages of intimidating and threatening in nature. It has become crucial for the government and people to have a concern about this phenomenon. There is little research, which focuses on the issue of cyberbullying and ethnicity.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Ethnocentrism

Ethnocentrism is a world-recognized syndrome of attitudes and behaviors. Watching one's in-group as virtuous and superior and an out-group as inferior and contemptible. The behaviors collaborated with ethnocentrism are cooperative relations with the in-group and absence of cooperative relations with the outgroup [2]. It was argued that partners of the ethnic group were typically observed in different items such as language, accent, physical features, or religion that were regarded as indicating common descent [3]. Despite the fact that ethnic conflict and war also generated

ethnocentrism [4]. Furthermore, ethnocentrism is in-group favoritism and out-group hostility. Ethnocentric behavior is an evolutionary process for a handle with members of one's in-group and the evolutionary process for dealing with members of other groups. A controversial study even says that the "clash of civilizations" is the greatest threat to world peace [5]. Moreover, In-group affiliation is the main topic for indent formation and identity politics [6]. Group membership boundaries become increasingly salient, closer and spatial contact between groups [7]. On another side, out-group hostility and in-group favoritism are different processes and it shows to be practical uncorrelated [8], [9]. To sum up, ethnocentrism shows the negative behavior within-group harmony, which bears the conflicts and biases toward one group or a person. Ethnocentrism is an output of a strong sense of ethnic group self-centeredness. It is coherence with intergroup preference, superiority, purity, virtues, and chastity, on other hand, shows the cohesion and devotion to the intragroup. Ethnocentrism is important in some states for political phenomena.

2.2 Cyberbullying Behavior

Cyberbullying is a virtual form of the act that displays in the digital world and harms at least a person. Cyberbullying was defined by some countries. For instance, Czech Republic defines cyberbullying behavior as intentional misuse of ICTs through the internet and Mobile phones which psychologically damage someone. But some countries such as France also defines cyberbullying behavior differently. They defined that deliberately using cyberspace in a repeated hostile way that harms someone is called cyberbullying behavior [10]. More precisely, a broad definition provided by Smith et al., [11] cyberbullying is a deliberately electronic action that is carried out against a person or group in which the victim cannot defend themselves. Moreover, cyberbullying behavior is fulfilled through different digital media. Such as Facebook, Twitter, email, chat rooms, and many other sites [12].

Researchers do not have unity regarding the cyberbullying behavior result and its typology. For example Tokunaga [13] found that 20 to 40% of adolescence face cyberbullying minimum once in a life. While there is a study which suggest that cyberbullying behavior decrease with the increase of age [14]. On other hand, Raskauskas & Stoltz [15] found that cyberbullying happens more in older

age and traditional bullying happens at a younger age. Furthermore, they revealed that more cyberbullying perpetrators become more cyber victims also.

Due to the increase of internet facilities, cyberbullying behavior is now able to increase and extend in the virtual world, currently, many people have access to cell phones and other electronic devices especially the young generation and they outbreak in cyberbullying [16].

Some studies clarified that cyberbullying is a negative behavior, and about 66% of the young generation witness this behavior in their lifetime. Besides, it was argued that males of the participants agreed to say that cyberbullying is a normal behavior [17]. In addition, Faucher, Jackson, & Cassidy [18] argued that college students are more vulnerable to cyberbullying.

The current generation has access to cyber facilities. Which is used in social media, learning new skills, and education. Through electrical communication sometimes deviant behavior took place. And this harms the persons' self-esteem that is more lasting in the future repeatedly [19]. Moreover, cyberbullying and victim behavior has direct relations with cyber usages [20].

Olweus & Limber[21] and Musharraf et al. [22] proved that females became more victims and males became offenders. However, some studies found differently and are arguing that sex did have a significant difference between cyberbullying and cyber victimization [23].

2.3 The Afghan Diaspora on Social Media

The prominent dispersion of Afghan nationals is in Iran and Pakistan. Though they are across the globe. These people are using social media such as Facebook more than other apps. Furthermore, the second generation of Afghans are more literate and are more stuck in cyberspace especially on Facebook [1].

2.4 Facebook

Mark Zuckerberg, Andrew McCollum, and Eduardo Saverin launched Facebook in 2004 on the internet. Its initial interaction took place at Harvard University then it started at Stanford and Yale and it connects the whole globe [24].

Moreover, in the last ten years, internet access increased in Afghanistan by twelve percent, parallels social media also boomed. These cyber media represent nine percent of the Afghan young

generation's age range from eighteen to thirty. More specifically, ninety-five percent are using Facebook [1].

3. Objectives

It is as below;

- 1) To understand the relationship of Ethnocentrism of Afghan Facebook users with cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior.
- 2) To compare the Ethnocentric, cyberbullying, and cyber victim behavior with the age of the participants.
- 3) To differentiate the gender of Afghan Facebook users regarding Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victim behavior.

4. Hypotheses

It is as below;

H₁: Ethnocentrism would have a significant positive correlation with cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior.

H₂: Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior would have a significant positive correlation with age.

H₃: Gender would have a significant negative association with Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior.

5. Methodology

5.1 Design

Diagnosing the ethnocentric and cyberbullying behavior on Facebook is an important issue. For this purpose the quantitative correlational research design conducted from 425 participants as online Google Survey and offline from Kunduz, Afghanistan in 2019. The questionnaire was able to respond through self-report. The nature of this research data was purposive sampling technique which was successfully applied. Therefore, Facebook users' data was conducted.

5.2 Participants and procedure

Afghan Facebook users participated and its sample size is $N=425$, which consists of both gender males and females (294, 131) respectively. More precisely, the online Google survey sample size was $N=35$ and the offline sample size was $N=390$. The offline sample was taken from Kunduz province, Afghanistan, and online data was taken through social media by sending the google survey link to the friends and group on Facebook. The Link was opened for two months. Furthermore, the age of the participants ranges from 18 to 36 and it's $M=21.32$ and $SD=2.84$ are shown.

For online data collection, a secured google link was used. Participants completed the consent form for their contribution to the study and they could withdraw from the study anytime. There has been no time and space limit for them and all responses were anonymously collected. Data collection was taken in the participants' environment. Every individual had free time for self-reporting the data. For analyzing the data SPSS 24 version was used. The normality of data was checked and the boxplot outlier reviewed. There were some data on the upper bound outlier. The result with outlier and without outlier was checked luckily important change was not seen. Moreover, the normal curve was quite fine.

5.3 Measures

Demographic information was collected as Age (18 to 36), Gender (male 294, female 131), Education field (Law and political science 53, Agriculture 39, Psychology 66, Computer Science 28, Literature Department 74, Education Department 132, Veterinary 26, Islamic Studies 3, Medical Science 4), Current Job (students 375, teachers 19, unemployed 31), Per day internet usage, Current Dwelling (Kunduz Province 324, other provinces 101), Marital Status (married 68, single 357), and ethnicity of the participants.

5.4 Materials

Tools for data collection were launched and its specification is given below.

5.4.1 Ethnocentrism Scale

This scale has 22 items in which 15 are scored and others are for balancing the items. Its reliability range from .80 to .90. Questions 4, 7, and 9 are reversed. Moreover, Drop questions number 3, 6, 12, 15, 16, 17, and 19 were dropped out. The score range from 15 to 75. The higher score, indicate

the higher ethnocentric behavior [25]. For validity and information on this scale see: Neuliep, J. W. (2002). Assessing the Reliability and the validity of the Generalized Ethnocentrism Scale, *Journal of Intercultural Communication Research*, 31, 201-215.

Furthermore, the scale was translated and back-translated by the Kunduz academic staff from English to Dari and Pashto. Moreover, instead of the "Culture" word "Ethnicity" was included to understand the ethnicity superiority. Dari and Pashtu "Ethnicity" or "Qawm" means a common cultural among the tribe. The scale is written in Pashto, English, and Dari languages. For all 15 items, Cronbach Alpha reliability was .559. After that, it checked the option "Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted" option applied. It revealed to delete item number 7 and 9 and those items excluded, and reliability of Cronbach alpha reached .735 that is good reliability.

5.4.2 Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI)

This inventory has two parts first cyberbullying scale and the second cyber victim scale. Each of them has 14 items that are self-reportable. Moreover, its measuring system is on 4 Likert scale system such as 0= Never happened, 1= one time, 2=two times, 3=more than two times. This inventory has asked for generally aggressive cyber behavior. Sum of each sub-scale score range from (0-56). A higher score indicates higher cyber behavior. Moreover, the reliability of cyberbullying is .92 and the cyber victim is .80 [26].

In this study, the scale of the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI) tool has been translated and back-translated to the national languages (Pashtu and Dari) by the academicians, and the reliability of cyberbullying and cyber victimization was (.938, .961) respectively. Furthermore, it was asked from participants to recall the cyber behavior in the last 12 months and self-report them. Moreover, its original format of English also has been written with it. Furthermore, in the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI) the "Facebook" word is added instead of social media. Therefore, cyberbullying on Facebook was a research focus area.

6. Results

The statistical results are below.

Table 6.1

Descriptive statistic of Gender with usage of Facebook every day/minutes and Age of the participants

	N	Mean	Median	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Male	294	125.40	90	60	10	720	710
Female	131	81.44	60	30	10	330	320
Age	425	21.32	21	20	18	36	18

Table 6.1 shows the descriptive statistic of gender, age, and everyday usage of Facebook. The result numerates that there are 294 males and 131 females. Males use Facebook media for 125.4 minutes/day on average. On the other side, females use the Facebook app on average for 81.44 minutes/day. Moreover, the participants' age ranges from 18 to 36, and its means is 21.32 years.

Table 6.2

Descriptive statistic of Participants' Ethnicity and their current J

	Tajik	Pashtun	Hazara	Uzbek	Other minorities
N	233	119	19	42	12
Percentage	54.8	28	4.5	9.9	2.8

Table 6.2 enumerates the ethnicity of the participants in this study. Participants of the study are 54.8% Tajik, 28% Pashtun, 4.5% Hazara, 9.9% Uzbek, and 2.8% other minorities.

Table 6.3

Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product-Moment Correlations of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, cyber victim behavior, and age

	N	M	SD	ethnocentrism	cyberbullying behavior	Cyber-victim behavior	age
ethnocentrism	425	34.66	8.31	—			

cyberbullying behavior	425	7.42	9.90	.121*	—		
Cyber-victim behavior	425	6.55	10.47	.129**	.624**	—	
age	425	21.32	2.84	-.042	.017	.002	—

***p<.01. *p<.05.N=425. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 and 0.05 levels (2-tailed).*

Table 6.3 depicts Descriptive statistics and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient computed to assess the relationship among the ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, cyber victim behavior, and age.

Firstly, the result shows that there is a weak positive linear correlation between Ethnocentrism and cyberbullying behavior, $r = .121$, and $N = 425$. However, the correlation is significant ($p = .013$). Overall, ethnocentrism behavior does appear to associate with cyberbullying behavior.

Secondly, ethnocentrism has a weak positive linear correlation with cyber victim behavior, $r = .129$, and $N = 425$. So, these two variables association is also significant ($p = .008$). Moreover, ethnocentrism does appear to associate with cyber victim behavior.

Thirdly, the linear correlation between ethnocentrism and age is a negative association, $r = -.042$, and $N = 425$. Whereas, these two variables' correlation is not significant ($p = .391$). Generally, ethnocentrism does not appear to associate with the participants' age.

The other variables of table 3 depict the correlation among the cyberbullying behavior with cyber victim behavior and age of the participants. There is a very strong positive linear correlation between cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior, $r = .624$, and $N = 425$. However, the correlation is significant ($p < .000$). Overall, in this study cyberbullying behavior does appear to associate with cyber victim behavior.

Furthermore, there is a very weak positive correlation between cyberbullying behavior and age, $r = .017$, and $N = 425$. However, the correlation is not significant ($p = .723$). Overall, cyberbullying behavior does not appear to associate with the age of the participants.

Lastly, the correlation between cyber victim behavior and age numerated. The result shows these two variables are almost zero correlated, $r=.002$, $N=425$, and $p=.963$. In other words, these variables do not have a correlation with one another.

H₁: Ethnocentrism would have a significant positive correlation with cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior.

The H₁ hypothesis is accepted. It means ethnocentrism has a significant positive correlation with cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior. In other words, increasing ethnocentrism has a positive association with increasing cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior of the participants. Furthermore, the decrease of ethnocentrism is related to the decrease of cyberbullying behavior and decreasing of the cyber victim behavior also.

H₂: Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior would have a significant positive correlation with age.

The H₂ hypothesis is rejected. It means there is not a significant positive correlation between Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior with the age of the participants.

Table 6.4

Group Statistics and Independent Samples t-Test

	Male		Female		t(423)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
ethnocentrism	34.84	8.49	34.26	7.90	.661	.509
cyberbullying behavior	7.61	9.44	7.01	10.91	.577	.564
Cyber-victim behavior	6.36	9.97	6.98	11.55	-.567	.571

p>.05. N=425. T-test is not significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6.4 depicts an independent-samples t-test of gender with ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior. The mean comparison of male and female participants with ethnocentrism shows no significant difference. In other words, there is not a significant difference in

the mean scores of males ($M=34.84$, $SD=8.49$) and females ($M=34.26$, $SD=7.90$) conditions; $t(423) = .661$, $p = .509$, on a two-tailed test. These results suggest that the gender of the participants does not affect ethnocentrism.

Secondly, the mean comparison of male and female participants with cyberbullying behavior shows no significant difference. In other words, there is not a significant difference in the mean scores of males ($M=7.61$, $SD=9.44$) and females ($M=7.01$, $SD=10.91$) conditions; $t(423) = .577$, $p = .564$, on a two-tailed test. These results suggest that the gender of the participants does not affect cyberbullying behavior.

Lastly, the mean comparison of male and female participants with cyber victim behavior shows no significant difference. In other words, there is not a significant difference in the mean scores of males ($M=6.36$, $SD=9.97$) and females ($M=6.98$, $SD=11.55$) conditions; $t(423) = -.567$, $p = .571$, on a two-tailed test. These results suggest that the gender of the participants does not affect cyber victim behavior.

H_3 : Gender would have a significant negative association with Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior.

The H_3 hypothesis is rejected because there is no significant difference between the gender of the participants with ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behaviors, and cyber victim behavior.

7. Discussion

The current research investigated how Ethnocentrism correlates with Cyberbullying behavior on Facebook. It revealed that ethnocentrism has a significant positive linear association with cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior ($p=.013$, $p=.008$) respectively. Besides that increasing, the ethnocentrism behavior directly increases cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior in using Facebook. However, ethnocentrism did not significantly correlate with age ($p=.391$).

Meanwhile, the correlation between cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior has a strong positive significant linear correlation ($p<.000$). It stipulated that decreasing cyberbullying behavior directly decreases the cyber victim behavior and vice versa. Moreno-Ruiz et al.[27] also proved that

cyberbullying and cyber victimization behavior has a positive relationship. However, they testified that the adolescent is higher in cyberbullying behavior.

Association of age with ethnocentrism, cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior showed a non-significant result in the study. However, Sevcikova & Šmahel[14] discovered differently about the age and cyberbullying and victim behavior. They argued that age has significant negative association with the cyberbullying and victim behavior but Raskauskas & Stoltz [15] found vice versa.

Furthermore, male and female differences were tested with ethnocentrism behavior, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior. It showed no-significant ($p=.509$, $p=.564$, and $p=.571$) difference among the gender of the participants. Similarly, Minor et al. [23] documented that gender does not have any significant relations with cyberbullying and cyber victimization. But

Olweus & Limber[21] and Musharraf et al. [22] showed that gender has significant difference with cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior.

8. Conclusion

The study proved that ethnocentrism has a significant contribution to cyberbullying & cyber victimization of Afghan Facebook users. On other hand, it revealed that age of the individual did not contribute significantly to cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and ethnocentrism of the participants. Lastly, it discovered that the gender of the individual did not contribute significantly to cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and ethnocentrism behavior of the participants.

9. Limitations

After the sincere efforts, there were certain drawbacks and limitations in the present study. Some of them are as follows.

After data collection personal contact was taken with 12 participants purposively for not responding my online survey. Most of the online participants argued that due to weak internet the questionnaire was not opening normally. On other hand, some argued that they could not trust the online system questionnaire. Besides this, some argued that we were afraid that someone would misuse our

identity. Even though, few said that they did not understand the usage of the online questionnaire. Because of these reasons, just 35 online participants contributed to the study.

10. Suggestions

There are some good suggestion for the Afghan society and Afghan Government as below;

1. To capture the real reason for cyberbullying and cyber victimization needs mixed-method research.
2. By observing the internet usage the government must put a restriction on obsessive Facebook users.
3. For generating income from Facebook users is the best source government must levy taxes on social media and its users.

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Appendix

List of Appendices

Appendix A: Demographic
Appendix B: Ethnocentrism Scale
Appendix C: Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI).....
Appendix D: Link of google survey.....

Appendix A: Demographic

د کنډز پوهنتون
 د حقوقو او سیاسي علومو پوهنځی
 په افغانستان کې د فیسبوک کارونه او د ملیت رابطه د انټرنیټي قلداری سره
 Ethnocentrism correlates with Cyber bullying on Facebook in Afghanistan

پرلپسې شمیره: _____ تاریخ: 1398/ /

پښتومتن: د دې څیړني مؤخه د فیسبوک کاروني کچه او اغيزې معلومل دی . تاسو ډاډه اوسئ چې هويت او شخصي معلومات مو خوندي ساتل کيږي. په دې پوښتنلیک کې سم یا ناسم ځواب نشته، یواځې ستاسو شخصي نظریاتو پورې اړه لري . نو له تاسو څخه په درنښت هیله کوو، چې هرې پوښتنې ته د خپلې خوبني ځواب په ورکولو زموږ سره مرسته وکړئ . د پام وړ ځواب په ټاکلو سره موږ مندوی کړئ.

English text: In this research, we will measure the effect of Facebook. We assure you that your identity will be save confidentially. This questionnaire do not have right or wrong answer, it belongs to your own perspective. We highly request you for participating me in this research. Thank you.

متن دري: هدف از راه اندازی این تحقیق معلوم نمودن سطح استفاده و تاثیرات، فیسبوک میباشد. به شما اطمینان داده میشود که هويت و معلومات شخصی تان مخفی میماند. در این پرسشنامه سوالات صحیح و غلط وجود ندارد، ولی همهء موضوعات آن به نظریات شخصی تان ارتباط دارد. بناءً از شما صمیمانه تقاضا مینمایم تا در قسمت ارایه جوابات به این پرسشنامه ما را همکاری نموده ممنون سازید.

رضایت نېنه / نشانی رضایت:

ډیموگرافیک (Demographic) :

۱: جنسیت (Gender): _____

۲: مدنی حالت/حالت مدنی (Marital status): مجرد (Single) متاهل (Married)

۳: په یوه ورځ کې له فیسبوک څخه د استفادې کچه (په دقیقو) /میزان استفاده از فیسبوک (دقیقه در روز)

_____ (Per day Facebook use (minutes)):

۴: تحصیلی څانگه/رشته تحصیلی (Educational Field): _____

۵: عمر/سن (Age): _____

۶: د زده کړې کچه/میزان تحصیلات (Educational Qualification): _____

- ۷: وظیفه (Job) - _____
- ۸: ملیت (یعنی تاجک، پشتون، هزاره..... و غیره) (Ethnicity): _____
- ۹: اصلی هستوگنخی / مسکونه اصلی (permanent dwelling): _____
- ۱۰: آیا تاسو فیسبوک کاروئ؟ / آیا شما از فیسبوک استفاده میکنید؟ (Do you use Facebook?)

Appendix B: Ethnocentrism Scale

لاندی جملې له نړیوال کلتوری تفاوت سره لیکل شوی دی. تاسو په عاجله توګه هغه ځواب انتخاب کړئ کوم چې تاسو نظر مطابق وي. دلته کوم غلط او صحیح ځواب نشته. په پنځو اندازه کې هغه اندازه انتخاب کړئ کومه چې تاسو ته مناسبه ښکاري.

Below are items that relate to the cultures of different parts of the world. Work quickly and record your first reaction to each item. There are no right or wrong answers. Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each item using the following five-point scale:

جملات ذیل به اساس تفاوت کلتورهای جهان نوشته شده است. شما عاجلاً یک جواب مطابق میل تان انتخاب کنید. در اینجا کدام جواب درست و غلط وجود ندارد. مطابق واحد اندازه پنج یک اندازه را، که به نظر شما مناسب باشد، انتخاب کنید.

Strongly Disagree (S.Dis) / شدیداً مخالف = 1

Disagree (Dis) / مخالف = 2

Neutral (N) / بیطرف = 3

Agree (Agr) / موافق = 4

Strongly Agree (S.Agr) / شدیداً موافق = 5

S.Dis	Dis	N	Agr	S.Agr	Item	No.
1	2	3	4	5	<p>زمور د قوم په پرتله نور قومونه روسته پاتې دي.</p> <p>Most other ethnicities are backward compared to my ethnicity.</p> <p>اکثر قوم های دیگر نسبت به قوم منعقب مانده است.</p>	1
1	2	3	4	5	<p>زما قوم باید نورو قومونو لپاره یوه اولگو وي.</p> <p>My ethnicity should be the role model for other ethnicities.</p> <p>قوم من باید به قومهای دیگر یک الگو باشد.</p>	2
1	2	3	4	5	<p>د نورو قومونو خلک چې زمور قوم ته راشي ناعادي چلند کوي.</p> <p>People from other ethnicities act strangely, when they come to my ethnicity.</p> <p>مردم از قوم بیگانه با قوم من برخورد متفاوت می کند.</p>	3
1	2	3	4	5	<p>د نورو قومونو ژوند، زمور د ژوند په څیر دی.</p> <p>Lifestyles in other ethnicities are just as valid as those in my</p>	4

					ethnicity. شبیوه زندگی در قوم های دیگر مثل زندگی قوم من است.	
1	2	3	4	5	5 نور قومونه باید کوبنبنس وکری چی زمور د قوم په خیر شی. Other ethnicities should try to be more like my ethnicity. قوم های دیگر باید کوشش کنند تا مثل قوم من باشند.	
1	2	3	4	5	6 زه د نورو قومونو له ارزښتونو او دودونو سره ډیره لیوالتیا نه لرم. I am not interested in the values and customs of other ethnicities. من به ارزشها و عنعنات قوم دیگر دلچسپی زیاد ندارم.	
1	2	3	4	5	7 د نورو قومونو په پرتله زمور خلک ډیر څه زده کوي. People in my ethnicity could learn a lot from people in other ethnicities. در قوم من مردم زیاد چیزها را یاد میگیرند نسبت به قوم دیگر.	
1	2	3	4	5	8 د نورو قومونو ډیر خلک په دې نه پوهیږی چی کوم شی دوی ته ښه دی. Most people from other ethnicities just do not know what is good for them. اکثر مردم قومهای دیگر به این نمی فهمند که کدام چیزها برای شان خوب است.	
1	2	3	4	5	9 زه د نورو قومونو ارزښتونو او دودونو ته درناوی لرم. I respect the values and customs of other ethnicities. من به ارزشها و عنعنات قوم دیگر را احترام نمیگذارم.	
1	2	3	4	5	10 نور قومونه زما تر قوم ډیر ښه دی. Other ethnicities are smart to look up to our ethnicity. قوم های دیگر نسبت به قوم ما بسیار خوب هست.	
1	2	3	4	5	11 که خلک زمور د قوم په خیر ژوند کړي وای، نو دوی به خوشحاله ول. Most people would be happier if they lived like people in my ethnicity. اگر مردم مثل قوم من زندگی می کرد این شان خوش آیند تر ميبود.	
1	2	3	4	5	12 زه په نورو قومونو کې ډیر ملگری لرم. I have many friends from different ethnicities. مناز قومهای دیگر دوست های زیادی دارم.	

1	2	3	4	5	<p>13 زما قوم تر بلهر چا بنه ژوند لری.</p> <p>People in my ethnicity have just about the best lifestyles of anywhere.</p> <p>مردم قوم من نسبت به هر شخص قوم دیگر، زندگی عالی دارند.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>14 د ژوند طرز په نورو قومونو کې زموږ د قوم په اساس اعتبار نه لری.</p> <p>Lifestyles in other ethnicities are not as valid as those in my ethnicity.</p> <p>طرز ندگی در قومهای دیگر نسبت به طرز زندگی، قوم من اعتبار ندارد.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>15 زه د نورو قومونوله ارزښتونو سره ډیره لیوالتیا لرم.</p> <p>I am very interested in the values and customs of other ethnicities.</p> <p>من به ارزشهای قوم دیگر دلچسپی عمیق دارم.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>16 زه د خپل قوم ارزښتونو سره سم نور قومونه پرتله کوم.</p> <p>I apply my values when judging people who are different.</p> <p>من به اساس ارزشهای قوم دیگران را قضاوت میکنم.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>17 زه هغه خلک باتقوا بولم چي زما په څیر دی.</p> <p>I see people who are similar to me as virtuous.</p> <p>من آن مردم را با تقوا میبینم که مثل من میباشد.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>18 زه له هغو خلکو سره چي متفاوت وی، کومک نه کوم.</p> <p>I do not cooperate with people who are different.</p> <p>من با کسانیکه متفاوت باشد کمک نمیکنم.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>19 زما د قوم ډیر خلک په دې نه پوهیږی چي کوم شی دوی ته ښه دی.</p> <p>Most people in my ethnicity just don't know what is good for them.</p> <p>اکثریت مردم قوم من به این نمیفهمند که کدام چیزها برای شان خوب است.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>20 زه په هغو خلکو اعتبار نه کوم، چي زما څخه متفاوت وی.</p> <p>I do not trust people who are different.</p> <p>من به افراد که متفاوت است اعتماد نمیکنم.</p>
1	2	3	4	5	<p>21 زما نه خوښیږی چي د نورو قومونو له خلکو سره اړیکي ولرم.</p> <p>I dislike interacting with people from different ethnicities.</p>

					من خوش ندارم که با مردمان قوم های دیگر تعامل داشته باشم.	
1	2	3	4	5	زه دنورو قومونو خلکو ته لبر درناوي لرم. I have little respect for the values and customs of other ethnicities. منبه ارزشها و عنعنات قوم های دیگر احترام کم دارم.	22

Appendix C: Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI)

په مهربانۍ سره لاندې جملې په احتیاط سره ولولئ. مهربانۍ وکړئ دا اوایاست چې په تیرو ۱۲ میاشتو کې لاندې اعمال تاسو سره واقع شوی دی یا تاسو بل چا سره کړي دی.

Please read the items carefully. Please tell us how know, often the instances described below have happened to you and you have done them to others during the last 12 months.

لطفاً جملات ذیل را به احتیاط بخوانید. لطفاً بگویند که در ۱۲ ماه گذشته اعمال پایل همراهی تان واقع شده یا شما همراهی دیگران انجام دادید.

Never (N) / هیڅکله نه / هیڅگاه = 0

Once (once) / یو وارې / یک دفعه = 1

Two to three times (Tw -Thr) / دو ناسه دفعه / ددوه تر درې ځلې = 2-3

More than three times (M.Thr) / بیشرت از سه دفعه / له درې ځلو زیات = >3

0= never, 1=once, 2-3=two to three times, >3=more than three times

نوت: هدف از این بخش سوالات، تحلیل رفتار مرتکب جرم سایبری میباشد. خواندم: <input type="checkbox"/> نوت: د دې برخې د پوښتنو مؤخه د سایبري مجرمینو د چلند څیرنه ده. ومي لوستل: <input type="checkbox"/>					
No.	Cyberbullying behavior	Tw - Thr	M.Thr	Once	N
1	سایبری ځورونکي چلند آزار رفتار سایبری له فیسبوک څخه شخصي معلومات را پټول. stealing of personal information form computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info) دزدین معلومات شخصي از فیسبوک.	2-3	>3	1	0
2	د کمپیوټر تخلص یا صفحي نوم غلا کول. stealing of computer nicknames or screen names دزدی کردن تخلص یا نام صفحه کمپیوتر.	2-3	>3	1	0
3	فیسبوک کپبه آنلاین توگه گوښل. threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter) تهدید به صورت آنلاین در فیسبوک.	2-3	>3	1	0
4	فیسبوک کې په آنلاین توگه سپکول. فیسبوک کې په آنلاین توگه سپکول.	2-3	>3	1	0

				Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter) توهين به صورت آنلاين در فيسبوك.	
0	1	2-3	>3	په آنلاين توگه د نورو محرومول يعنى د بل شخص بلاک کول يا کمنټ (تبصره) يې حذفول. excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them محروم کردن ديگران از طريق آنلاين با بلاک کردن يا حذف کردن کمنټ (تبصره).	5
0	1	2-3	>3	د انټرنيت له لاري د جعلی عکسونو په پوست کولو سره تهمت کول. slander by posting fake photos on the internet از طريق انټرنيت، تهمت بستن توسط عکس های جعلی و آن را نشر (پوست) کردن.	6
0	1	2-3	>3	د بل شخص له خبرولو څخه بغير د هغه شخصی انټرنيتی ارتباطاتو استعمالول. sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room) استعمال انټرنيت شخصی بدون خبر دادن به آن مثلاً توسط فيسبوك مسنجر همراي ديگران ارتباطات برقرار کردن.	7
0	1	2-3	>3	د آنلاين تبصرو له لاري د بل کس په کمنټو ريشخند و هل. Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook) از طريق تبصره های آنلاين به ديگران ريشخند زدن.	8
0	1	2-3	>3	د ايميل له لاري گواښونه يا مضره کمنټونه ور ليرل. Sending threatening or hurtful comments through email از طريق ايميل اخطار و يا کمنټ های مضر را روان کردن.	9
0	1	2-3	>3	ايميلونه غلاکول (د يوزر نوم، پاسورډ) او اصلی مالک يې بلاکول. stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access دزدی کردن توسط ايميل (نام يوزر. پاسورډ) و مالک اصلی آن را بلاک کردن.	10
0	1	2-3	>3	د ايميل لاس رسی غلاکول او د هغوی شخصی پيغامونه لوستل. stealing email access and reading personal messages دست رسی به ايميل ها را دزدی کردن و معلومات شخص را خواندن.	11
0	1	2-3	>3	اخطار يه ورکول او يا مضره پيغام ليرل. sending threatening and or hurtful text messages اخطار يه دادن و يا پيام های مضر را فرستادن.	12
0	1	2-3	>3	د بل جنسيت (نارينه / بنځينه) په صفت ځان بنودل. misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female)	13

				خود را به صفت جنسیت (مرد/زن) متفاوت نشان دادن.	
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>14</p> <p>په آنلاين طريقه پرته له اجازې، شرمونكي عكسونه خپرول.</p> <p>publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission</p> <p>از طريق آنلاين بدون اجازه، عكس های مبتذل و رسوا كننده را پخش و نشر كردن.</p>	

Never (N) / هیڅکله نه / هیچگاه = 0

Once (once) / یوواری / یک دفعه = 1

Two to three times (Tw -Thr) / دو تا سه دفعه / دو ځلې = 2-3

More than three times (M.Thr) / بیشتر از سه دفعه / له درې ځلو زیات = >3

0= never, 1=once, 2-3=two to three times, >3=more than three times

<p>نوت: هدف از این بخش سوالات تحلیل رفتار، شخص متضرر جرایم سایبری است. خواندم <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>نوت: د دې برخې پوښتنو مؤخه د سایبري جرمونو څخه د زیانمن شویو کسانو د چلند څیرل دي. و مي لوستل <input type="checkbox"/></p>					
				Cyber victim behavior	سایبری زیانمن چلند
N	Once	Tw - Thr	M.Thr		No.
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>له فیسبوک څخه شخصی معلومات را پټول.</p> <p>stealing of personal information form computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info)</p> <p>دزدین معلومات شخصی از فیسبوک.</p>	1
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>د کمپیوټر تخلص یا صفحي نوم غلا کول.</p> <p>stealing of computer nicknames or screen names</p> <p>دزدی کردن تخلص یا نام صفحه کمپیوتر.</p>	2
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>فیسبوک کپیه آنلاين توگه گواښل.</p> <p>threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)</p> <p>تهدید به صورت آنلاين در فیسبوک.</p>	3
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>فیسبوک کي په آنلاين توگه سپکول.</p> <p>Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)</p> <p>توهين به صورت آنلاين در فیسبوک.</p>	4
0	1	2-3	>3	<p>په آنلاين توگه د نورو محرومول یعنی د بل شخص بلاک کول یا کمنټ (تبصره) یی حذفول.</p> <p>excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them</p>	5

				محروم کردن دیگران از طریق آنلاین با بلاک کردن یا حذف کردن کمنت (تبصره).	
0	1	2-3	>3	د انترنیت له لاري د جعلی عکسونو په پوست کولو سره تهمت کول. slander by posting fake photos on the internet از طریق انترنیت،تهمت بستن توسط عکس های جعلی و آن را نشر(پوست) کردن.	6
0	1	2-3	>3	د بل شخص له خبرولو څخه بغیر د هغه شخصی انترنیتی ارتباطاتو استعمالول. sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room) استعمال انترنیت شخصی بدون خبر دادن به آن مثلاً توسط فیسبوک مسنجر همراي دیگران ارتباطات برقرار کردن.	7
0	1	2-3	>3	د آنلاین تبصرو له لاري د بل کس په کمنټو ریشخند و هل. Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook) از طریق تبصره های آنلاین به دیگران ریشخند زدن.	8
0	1	2-3	>3	د ایمیل له لاري گواښونه یا مضره کمنټونه ورلیزل. Sending threatening or hurtful comments through email از طریق ایمیل اخطار و یا کمنت های مضر را روان کردن.	9
0	1	2-3	>3	ایمیلونه غلاکول (د یوزر نوم، پاسورډ) او اصلی مالک یی بلاکول. stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access دزدی کردن توسط ایمیل (نام یوزر. پاسورد) و مالک اصلی آن را بلاک کردن.	10
0	1	2-3	>3	د ایمیل لاس رسی غلاکول او د هغوی شخصی پیغامونه لوستل. stealing email access and reading personal messages دست رسی به ایمیل ها را دزدی کردن و معلومات شخص را خواندن.	11
0	1	2-3	>3	اخطاریه ورکول او یا مضره پیغام لیزل. sending threatening and or hurtful text messages اخطاریه دادن و یا پیام های مضر را فرستادن.	12
0	1	2-3	>3	د بل جنسیت (نارینه / بنځینه) په صفت ځان بنودل. misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female) خود را به صفت جنسیت (مرد/زن) متفاوت نشان دادن.	13
0	1	2-3	>3	په آنلاین طریقہ پرته له اجازي، شرمونکي عکسونه خپرول. publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission از طریق آنلاین بدون اجازه، عکس های مبتذل و رسوا کننده را پخش و نشر کردن.	14

